

Comparing locals' and non-locals' perceptions of places via social media reviews

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Summary

In this paper, we emphasise that people with different personal experiences develop different perceptions of places. We distinguish between locals and non-locals based on users' digital footprints provided by social media data. Afterwards, we applied Long Short Term Memory to capture people's feelings, either positive or negative, over different places. We further extract keywords that are often used in the reviews and make a comparison between those from locals and non-locals by using Word2Vec and Clustering. Ultimately, we aim to contribute to the literature of place semantics by including sentimental analysis based on social media.

KEYWORDS: Place Perceptions; Feeling Map; Point of Interests; Natural Language Processing

1. Background

We examine whether there are differences in the way that 'locals' and 'non-locals' score and perceive places, represented using Points Of Interests (POIs) from the Yelp Open Dataset. Based on the timestamps and geolocation of users' check-in footprints, we first develop a method to distinguish between those who live locally and those who are non-locals. We then use natural language processing and machine learning methods to extract the 'feelings' (positive or negative) and 'perceptions' (i.e., words people used to describe the places) these two groups of people have towards various places. We aim to contribute to the use of AI and data science to explore how places, and the values we ascribe to them, reflect the subjective human perception of living environments based on context and experience, and how people develop different perceptions of place, depending on their personal experiences.

2. Data & Methodology

We will introduce how to use deep learning and machine learning methods to obtain people's feelings and perceptions of places below. We chose New Orleans as a case study and collected data from Yelp's open dataset, which contains POIs, user and review information. The workflow of the proposed method is shown in Figure 1.

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Figure 1. The technical diagram of this work.

We draw on Rofè (2004)’s “feeling map” idea, which surveys and maps people’s emotional responses to their environment. In our work, we opted for deep learning methods to obtain people’s feelings from their reviews rather than conducting interviews. We applied a classic Long Short Term Memory neural architecture to classify feelings in people’s reviews, which captures contextual semantic information and is effective in text classification (Elman, 1990) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Long Short Term Memory Architecture (Source: Own elaboration based on Hochreiter & Schmidhuber(1997)).

After feeling classification of reviews, following the view that the occurrence and frequency of words in people’s reviews mirror their primary concerns about that place (Hausmann et al., 2020; Wan et al., 2021), we extracted nouns, verbs, adjectives and adverbials with frequency greater or equal to 3 from feeling groups (positive, neutral and negative) separately. We used Word2Vec to convert words into vectors suitable for machine learning algorithms to process. We then clustered the high-frequency word vectors based on their semantical similarities to obtain cluster centre words (i.e. representing

features) by using K-Means++ and K-Dimensional Tree. To visualise our clustering results in two-dimensional space, we performed dimensionality reduction through T-distributed stochastic neighbour embedding.

3. Result

3.1 Eliminate the noise caused by nonlocals data

We used two methods for identifying locals from social media users based on their check-in footprints. The first method ('timestamp') is to calculate the time difference between a user's first and last review in New Orleans, considering reviews with a time difference greater than 10 days as locals. The second method ('geolocation') is inspired by previous work on identifying locals from social media users (Zhang et al., 2020), the user who leaves the most reviews in a city can be regarded as a local of that city, we set the threshold as 50%. The results are shown in Table 1. The large difference in the number of locals and nonlocals determined by the two methods is due to the presence of inactive users. That is, some people only used Yelp briefly (within 10 days), but they did not leave footprints in other cities either. To mitigate the impact of inactive users, we selected 37417 users identified as locals by both methods for further analysis.

Table 1 The Number of Locals and Nonlocals.

Year	Timestamp	Geolocation	Intersection
Locals(person)	43970	215986	37417
Nonlocals(person)	201499	29483	\

3.2 Find divisive POIs from feeling maps

We calculated the number of various feelings types received by each Business_ID from locals and non-locals respectively, and generated the feeling map based on the type with the largest number(Figure 3). Our focus then shifted to areas where feeling differences existed between locals and non-locals, leading us to create Figure 4, which illustrates the distribution of divisive POIs. To explain the factors influencing feeling differences among people in various areas, we conducted kernel density estimation (Figure 5) based on the check-in frequency of locals and non-locals. This analysis help us identify areas that are popular with two groups. Additionally, we calculated the proportion of each type contributing to these divisive areas, as depicted in Figure 6. Notably, we found that Restaurants, Nightlife, and food POI are more likely to elicit divisive feelings between locals and non-locals, whereas POI types, such as Active Life, showed minimal difference in feelings between locals and non-locals.

Figure 3 Feeling Maps Depicting the Feeling Types (the type with the most number) for Each Business_ID by Locals (above) and Non-locals (below).

Figure 4 Feelings of locals(left) and non-locals(right) towards divisive POIs.

Figure 5 Frequency of check-ins to divisive POIs by locals(left) and non-locals(right).

Figure 6 Rank of POI Categories Most Visited by Locals and Non-locals Among Divisive POI types.

Figure 8 Word2Vec Visualisation of Positive Restaurants Reviews From Non-Locals.

Table 3 The Most Frequent Words of Each Cluster.

Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4	Cluster 5
brought	particular	yeah	kitchen	aioli
moved	type	know	cute	meatballs
coming	kind	maybe	homey	pesto
put	anyway	suppose	porch	bordelaise
went	certainly	think	beautiful	dessert

4. Conclusion and Future Work

We presented preliminary semantic information mining using social media review data to discern differences in feelings and perceptions attached to place between locals and non-locals. The word extraction parts needs further exploration. Currently, we have attempted to use the K-D tree method to obtain potential features from all clusters that can represent people’s perceptions of different types of POI. However, the results generated by this algorithm is challenging to analyse, as shown in table 2&3. Nevertheless, upon examining the results of Word2Vec visualisation (Figure 7&8) using the restaurants as an example, we observe that locals’ negative emotion are often linked to aspects such as food type (salads, sandwiches, etc.) and price (bill, dollars etc.). Conversely, non-locals’ positive emotions are associated with factors like the atmosphere (romantic, pleasant etc.). Next, we aim to discover more effective ways to identify differences in the wording used by locals and non-locals to describe POI types. We plan to apply our model to other POI types, then we can get better understanding of how the attention of locals and non-locals to different POI types impacts their feelings towards the community.

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Biographies

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Richard Harris is Professor of Quantitative Social Geography at the University of Bristol. He is interested in socio-spatial inequalities within society and their causes, and likes doing things with data and running. Sometimes those interests combine.